

D3.5

User needs beyond academic research for Computational Literary Analysis

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Abstract

In spite of decades of studies and manifestos arguing for the ‘use’ of the humanities for various purposes, from their capacity to form citizens (Nussbaum, 1998, 2010) through to more specific appeals to their potential to improve technology development (Madsbjerg, 2017), the idea of an ‘applied humanities’ has yet to fully take explicit hold within our training and research paradigms. In spite of this, however, appeals to the very humanities-relevant power of narrative and storytelling seem ever more present in new journalism, brand narratives, and even narrative economics (Shiller, 2019). While these questions may not have a significant impact on the day-to-day work of the average individual scholar, they are of significant importance for the builder of infrastructure. For this reason, we reviewed literature on applications of fiction, literary studies, or CLS outside of the academy to identify professionals that could benefit from this CLS infrastructure. In conversations with those professionals, we aimed to understand how the field would have to further develop to take into account the needs specific to their field. In the first section, the literature review of the CLS INFRA D3.5 report aims to make transparent the utility of the potential infrastructure (answering also the question of utility *for whom*) instead of taking the risk of obscuring its applicability through consideration of data collections, services, communication channels, and other design choices underpinning research infrastructures. This report explores not only the needs and methods of currently known and clearly emerging user groups but also of potential users from outside of the academy. The second section on the interviews describes potential user stories and requirements from 15 focussed interviews with professionals from the field of policy, journalism, art, consultancy publishing, medicine, and bibliotherapy. From these conversations, we infer potential use case scenarios for applications of literature and CLS beyond academia.

1. Introduction

In research infrastructure development, a balance must always be struck between depth and breadth. If conceived of too broadly, an initiative can lose its precision or specificity, rendering it ill-suited to the task of supporting the development of new knowledge. Defined too narrowly, however, the pool of users it can serve may not be sufficient to make a case for return on the investment required to build it, or may miss opportunities to foster interdisciplinary and intersectoral knowledge exchange.

The CLS INFRA project has been a 4-year initiative to instigate the development of bespoke infrastructure for the field of computational literary studies. At the same time, the project has been exploring precisely this question of scale, both in terms of a) maximising access for the existing categories of users for such resources (such as literary, linguistic and computational researchers at every career stage), and also in terms of b) understanding the needs of potential new users engaged perhaps not in academic research, but in the adjacent tasks of developing and applying knowledge from literary (or literary adjacent) sources.

The project’s efforts toward the first of these two trajectories is contained elsewhere in its documentation, for instance in the reports of its TNA Fellows and Training Schools. Deliverable 3.5 (in essence, this report) consolidates the results of this second pathway, asking the challenging hypothetical questions: “if an infrastructure for computational literary studies were to exist, would users from outside of literary studies make use of it? If so, how

would that infrastructure need to be designed to meet their needs?” In the course of developing this report, its authors came to refer to this as the central “double counterfactual:” the methods for using computational literary infrastructure in an applied setting don’t yet exist, in part because the infrastructure to allow them to emerge doesn’t yet exist. And yet, many of the results from this work do point toward a significant untapped potential, indicating many sectors and individual roles that do, in fact, use literature, narrative or storytelling to advance their work in applied settings.

The work was not able to begin from this point, however. In order to determine the fit between any sort of literary methods and activities taking place in industry or other non-research organisational setting, we first had to turn our attention to the question of applied humanities and indeed applied literary studies. Only by doing so were we able to develop an appropriate boundary language to enable discussion of the potential futures of computational literary studies and its infrastructure with individuals for whom none of these terms held much inherent meaning. This accounts as well for our conscious decision not to be overly strict in our use of terminology around the object of the eventual infrastructure we were asking our interview participants to help us scope. For a literary scholar, the difference between a narrative conceived of, produced and published as literature and other forms of narrative or story may be vast, but these differences are scientific ones not always recognised outside of the fold of professional literary researchers. For this reason, we needed to keep our vocabulary somewhat more open than we might otherwise in order to progress our investigations. Given not just our positioning within a double counterfactual, but also our wider concerns about research infrastructures seeming closed to outsiders, it was important in our investigations to maintain this potential for conversation and exploration.

What follows is a consolidation of two years of exploratory research, organised according to the following headings: First, in section one, we present an overview of the current state of the art in terms of applied humanities approaches in general, and applied literary studies in specific. This exploration gave us a baseline for conducting our series of interviews with practitioners from a wide variety of roles and sectors, regarding the potential for applied literary approaches in their work, which are reported in detail in section two. These users work beyond academia, meaning that nearly all participants work in sectors that may have no connection to academic research at a university, especially in the fields of literary studies or librarianship. Instead, they work in sectors that would not necessarily see themselves as driven solely by the kinds of basic research imperatives that generally drive the humanities, focussing instead on applying knowledge to addressing other kinds of challenges. In section three, we use the interviews (which are also being released as an open research dataset) to extract user scenarios that can act as a guide in the development of literary data and tools that could act as well as industrial research infrastructures. In the final section, we conclude the report with a number of general recommendations for the future of this project of broadening our conceptualisation of the non-academic user of computational literary research infrastructure.

2. Literature Review, Applied Humanities and Applied Literary Studies

2.1 Theoretical Framework

In this chapter we argue, based on the existing heterogeneous body of work that theorises or enacts an applied approach to literary studies, that literature can function as evidence regarding the nature of culture, values and collective identities of the past and the present. To consider the possibility of fiction as evidence, it helps to assume a constructivist view on reality, which describes “knowledge not as truths to be transmitted or discovered, but as emergent, developmental, nonobjective, viable constructed explanations by humans engaged in meaning-making in cultural and social communities” (Fosnot, 2013), i.e. that an individual constructs a reality based on their cultural and social surroundings and explanations. Fiction is, in this context, “a shaper of identity communities” (Anderson, 1983) and a “laboratory of the possible” (Westphal, 2011, p. 63), which can show us probable scenarios, warn us against future threats, and prepare us for the unknown (Ameel & Craps, 2020).” (Edmond et al., [forthcoming 2024])

To explore the potential of applied literary studies, we need to position our understanding of the act of reading and viewing fiction in the following three ways; firstly, by understanding our perceptions of reality as highly contingent upon narratives we have consumed (Southgate, 2009; Behin, 2019), we can begin to theorise the margins of potential to apply insight from fiction for ‘real-world’ applications. Fiction makes visible “modes of presentation of situations and the connection of events that appear elsewhere to be imposed by the very obviousness of the real. In this way it can better teach us the multiple ways of creating a sense of reality and their links with the forms of the social order.” (Rancire, 2018, p. 270). Secondly, and related to the first point, we have to “demystify literature” (Behin, 2019, p. 25), because literature detached from “life world situations is an irrelevant entity” (Behin, 2019, p. 24). Thirdly, we have to embrace a nonlinear paradigm of reading fiction. Behin says that “literacy” does not matter as much for applied literature (2019, p. 27), as applied literature is a “context-oriented activity” in which literature deals with “context-bound issues” and is in a state of “flux” (Behin, 2019, p. 32)¹.

In the humanities and natural sciences alike, evidence is subject to the scientist’s biases and interpretations. See for example the example of electrical charge in cathode rays, as described by Achinstein (2001, p. 4): In 1883 Hertz designed experiments to determine whether cathode rays are electrically charged and saw his experiments’ result—no movement of the electrometer needle when cathode rays were produced and no deflection of from electrified plates—as evidence that they are not charged. Fourteen years later, Thompson repeated Hertz’s second experiment, got the same result, but did not read it as evidence for an absence of charge in the cathode rays, but hypothesised that the “if the cathode rays are charged particles, then when they pass through the gas in the cathode tube they ionize the gas molecules producing positive and negative charges that will neutralize the charge on the metal plates between which the cathode rays travel” (Achinstein, 2001, p. 4). Thompson was able to prove his hypothesis by modifying the experiment, showing that evidence does not always

¹ This is applicable to all our models except for literature as capacity building because this model often relies on a traditional reading paradigm.

mean decisive evidence. Furthermore, Leonelli suggests that data, “is a relational category applied to research outputs[...]They do not have truth-value in and of themselves, nor can they be seen as straightforward representations of given phenomena” within the contexts of the history of data production and use, particularly in biology (2015). Baker and Haraway both suggest that “the unbiased researcher” is a construct of the research community (Baker, 2006, p. 10) and that objectivity is impossible (Haraway, 1988). Timothy Williamson adds that “one's evidence consists of the totality of propositions that one knows” (Kelly, 2014; for more details see Williamson, 2000). Evidence is something that justifies belief (Kelly, 2014) and has a “public character” to it, i.e. “witnessing of experiments” has to be “a collective art” (Kelly, 2014). A literary corpus can function as a collective art, an accumulation of human beliefs and thoughts, as it is a collection of various descriptions, observations, and thoughts. Nikitina addresses that there are “misconceptions that science is just solid truth and that humanistic concepts are pure abstractions” (Nikitina, 2009, p. 43), and if these misconceptions are true, they are challenged when we question the nature of scientific data and evidence. They add that the “humanities refer to phenomena and tangible relationships in the real world and that the real world both learns from these ideas and metaphors and informs them in a reciprocal way” (Nikitina, 2009, p. 43), and we suggest that literature could help foregrounding these phenomena and relationships, and that this knowledge from literature could contribute to applications for various professionals.

The basis of theory and practise that we were able to assemble around the questions of applied literary studies is fragmented and uneven. In order to be able to bring some useful order to this heterogeneity, we developed and applied in our work the following taxonomy as a way to describe the uses or applications of literature, and potentially CLS tools, beyond the literary studies field: a) using fictional narratives as evidence for making claims about past and present cultural and historical identities and values (Southgate, 2014); b) using fictional narratives as a mechanism for specific capacity building, such as developing empathy (Thexton et al., 2019) c) using fictional narratives to build or access predictive models (Pinto & Medina, 2020; and Greenfield, 2021); d) using fictional narratives as a means to prototype future scenarios, cultures, identities and technologies (Atherton & Brewer, 2016). This taxonomy applies to using literature for academic research, but also beyond. The following sections discuss each of these approaches in turn, also particularly looking at how reading literature in large quantities, i.e. distant reading, data analytics (texts or textual elements as data) or CLS can reinforce the utility of literature for the purposes of working within them. The larger an assembled literary corpus is, the greater the likelihood that individual biases, positionalities or acts of imagination will appear as anomalies, while an aestheticised, but still representational, set of reflections on cultures and practices will emerge. By taking a corpus-based approach, CLS scholars can draw from a large number of individual works and perspectives, which can reduce the potential biases of individual authorship, a common barrier to the use of literature as evidence.

a. Literature as Evidence for Making Claims about Past and Present Cultural and Historical Identities

Pasco suggests viewing literature as a “historical archive” (2004, p. 373), and refers back to the works of “Lucien Febvre, Robert Darnton, Terry Castle, Felicity Nussbaum, Deidre Lynch, Terry Eagleton, Lynn Hunt, Susan Dunn, Mary Louise Roberts, Bruce Robbins, and others”

(2004, p. 373), who all support literature's potential to be used as historical evidence. Southgate (2009) argues that reality relies on subjective perception and thus history and fiction are closely related; one cannot exist without the other. Nevertheless, before using literature as historical evidence, one needs to consider a text's legitimacy and position in relation to a historical event, as numerous movements and generations of scholars have indicated. For instance, knowing Charles Dickens' background, we should avoid deducing historical claims about the French Revolution based on Dickens's *A Tale of Two Cities*. We can use it, however, to make claims about the mid-nineteenth-century British view on the French Revolution (Southgate, 2009, p. 8). The translation of texts can add another intercultural layer of complexity, and limitation on its possible use cases. For example, "Shakespeare's original text [Hamlet] forms the basis for an assessment of high British culture since 1601. Translated into Russian by Boris Pasternak, however, it becomes an index of Soviet and post-Soviet views about the recalcitrant prince" (Richmond-Garza, 2002, p. 508). In this context, one might also cite the New Historicist approach of treating "a literary text as a product of its time and social environment rather than a thing in itself" (Greenblatt & Callagher, 2000, p. 4), again emphasising the inseparable link between literature and history. Far more recently, Baumard et al. traced romantic elements in Eurasian, Ancient Greek, Roman literary fiction over the past millennium, and confirmed "that a higher level of economic development is strongly associated with a greater incidence of love in narrative fiction (our proxy for the importance of love in a culture)" (2022). The importance of the use of literature, rather than journalism or scientific discourse is of great importance here, as the words that they used as indicators of love in fiction, e.g. "amorous" and "infatuated" (2022), would be far less likely to occur in non-fictional texts, making literature a historical archive for measuring cultural and social sensemaking trends absent in other textual production of the time.

For journalists and policymakers, literature offers insight into voices and ideas that have been oppressed in the past. Literary authors could explore ideas more freely in literature because it has an "epistemological" privilege: it is not obliged to deny its fictional character" (Rancière, 2018, p. 270). Many American fiction authors like Walt Whitman, Mark Twain, Theodore Dreiser, and Ernest Hemingway left journalism to write about slavery, sexuality, and racism, with more political freedom (Fishkin, 1988, p. 7). Literature and journalism have thus a long history of cross-fertilization. Former Hungarian president Árpád Göncz argues that "In Hungary literature—especially poetry—has been the primary tool of national self-expression for centuries" because Hungary's "struggle against the Turkish occupation for 150 years offered precious little chance to talk politics" (1991, p. 10). Furthermore, literature can be used as evidence to back up arguments in policy, which helps to demonstrate in story form, how a political action or inaction could play out. For instance, abolitionists used Harriet Beecher Stowe's novel *Uncle Tom's Cabin* to advocate against slavery. The novel functioned as a warning that the cruelties against African American slaves as described in the novel would keep playing out in reality as long as slave owners kept their power. The novel did not merely describe slave's lives, its powerful storytelling moved many Americans towards political action. Abraham Lincoln famously said that Stowe was "the little woman who wrote the book that started this great war [the Civil War]," and although Lincoln's statement is hyperbolic, it emphasises the novel's political impact (Largent). Literature is a "distinctly effective system of ideological dissemination" (Richmond-Garza, 2002, p. 506) or as the poet Percy Shelley illustrates: "[poets are] the influence which is moved not, but moves. Poets are the unacknowledged legislators of the world" (2009, October 13). Fiction uses the power of language and storytelling to incite an emotional response in the audience. Identifying how language is used

to empower or delegitimise a political group, gives insights into the power dynamics, which is important for policy-making.

Beyond cultural, social, and political identities, literature can also serve as evidence to reconstruct geographical spaces. Literature can help us understand the complexity of geographical spaces and how they are perceived by different groups of people by offering multifocal perspectives to space. Westphal (2011) coined this way of understanding space “Geocriticism.” He argues that “[w]riting of space may always be singular, but the geocritical representation emerges from a spectrum of individual representations as rich and varied as possible.” (2011, p. 113). Learning about geographical space from fiction teaches us about the space’s multilayered and decentralised impact on the human minds interacting with it.

Narrative is not freed from the linear progression that was traditionally reserved for it; space has become recalcitrant to the classical dialectic that radically opposed the center and periphery. Narrative searches itself, as does space. Space becomes more complex and diversified, as does narrative.[...] Once again, the derealization of space leads to its fictionalization. Generalized fictionalization (the simulacrum of which Baudrillard speaks) necessarily leads literature and other forms of mimetic art into an original order, which requires a new approach to realism. (Westphal 2011, p. 163)

Literature provides non-linear descriptions of space as well as their emotional impact on people who are not necessarily in power. These spaces can e.g. be an archaeological site that can be reconstructed by combining historical novels, archaeological articles, and data². Plets, Huijnen, and Oeveren go beyond the descriptions of the physical space in archaeological texts (content level); they also trace within them biases caused by nationalist movements, as well as those movements’ influence on archaeological studies (language level) (2021). They conclude that “archeologists are[...]also being shaped by modern ideas of the nation and include these frames in their research questions,” and the authors “explored the past through the lens of 19th century identity constructions” (Plets, Huijnen, & Oeveren, 2021, p. 293), which uncovers biases in those archeologist’s research on a place. “[O]ver the past decades, archeologists have become aware of the politics of heritage” (Plets, Huijnen, & Oeveren, 2021, p. 293), so including more literature into archeological and geographical research could give new insight into those political and cultural backgrounds surrounding narratives of a place. In their research Plets, Huijnen, and Oeveren apply CLS-alike methods on academic archaeological texts, such as “word frequencies analysis of theoretical concepts” to determine “cultural-historical phrasings,” distant reading metadata, etc. (Plets, Huijnen, & Oeveren, 2021, p. 294). Literature could reveal to us exactly these (e.g. nationalist) biases and it could offer a critical lens on past findings. Wetzel (1988) attempts to develop a critical historical lens on Carthage by reading closely historical novels about the city. He describes the rich archaeological insights these novels offer, which shows how archeology and literature can benefit from cross-fertilisation. Accessibility to a large corpus of literary works can enrich the research field by layering individual accounts against canonised narratives of history or space.

Using CLS and literature as evidence can also potentially help professionals in the industry, such as publishing or the entertainment industry (e.g. Netflix). The entertainment or publishing industry may want to look at literature that an audience is currently drawn to and release

² e.g. if one combines Wetzel’s 1988 and Plets’, Huijnen’s, and Oeveren’s 2021 approaches to understanding the history behind an archaeological site.

movies and novels within that genre. For instance, if there is an audience for Jane Austen's novels, then there is most likely also an audience that would receive well movies about her novels (e.g. *Pride and Prejudice*, 2005) or her life (e.g. *Becoming Jane*, 2007). Or perhaps the audience desires to read novels following "the marriage plot" in which a woman and a man in love need to overcome obstacles to end up together or get married. With the help of literary or film research, trends can be adapted to the audience's desires or to expand the audience's horizon by e.g. the recent increase in inclusion of LGBTQ+ protagonists in novels and movies (e.g. *Red, White, and Royal Blue*, 2023). Distant reading can observe what cultural or identity concerns certain audiences find important, which can be invaluable information to the cultural and entertainment sector. For instance, audiences in Germany or the US would find the presence of LGBTQ+ characters more appealing than audiences in Russia (Fischer, 2013, June 5). One can learn which books, movies, or other media would sell best in a country or region based on contemporary literary trends: indeed, Archer and Jockers developed in their study, published as *The Bestseller Code* (2006), an algorithm that could predict a manuscript's chance at succeeding based on common characteristics in bestselling novels through data mining and corpus analysis. *The Riddle of Literary Quality* (2023) by Dalen-Oskam is a more recent example of identifying the "literariness" in contemporary Dutch novels, as evaluated by 14,000 readers, with the help of computational tools. A similar idea underpins the project *Möbius*, a user-focused research initiative funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme. It uses a "prosumer intelligence toolkit" that "will allow publishers to better understand how global readers relate to books, their characters, and storylines. While Möbius does not specify whether it uses literature as primary research data, literature can help to inform business models for publishing industries, a strategy similar to that of *The Bestseller Code*. Data analysis will be possible thanks to an interactive data visualisation and a user-friendly dashboard for professional use (*Möbius*). CLS tools can detect trending narrative structures, which can allow publishing and entertainment companies to better adapt to evolving reading trends. Alternatively, they can use the knowledge of current trends to introduce new ideas with a better understanding of established clichés.

All these examples show that literature has the potential to be or has already been deployed as evidence in various fields, mainly because it informs us about human cultural identities in a way that common forms of social or market research would struggle to represent. The way in which literature informs us through empathy and stories points to its potential to develop ideas and capacities, which will be the more specific focus of the next section.

b. Literature as Capacity Building

Literature and the study of literature can build various human capacities and, as such, can afford the improvement of individual and social well-being. Literature helps us to study and promote empathy, (see Kidd and Castano, 2013; Tamir et al., 2016; Hunt, 2008, starting from 25:00) or "analytical empathy" (Madsbjerg, 2017), i.e. the ability to understand human behaviour in a cultural context. This capacity becomes even more important as we are surrounded by technological platforms which overwhelm and desensitise our ability to empathise (Turkle, 2015), or as we are living in an increasingly data-focused society with algorithms that "do many things but they will never actually give a damn" (Madsbjerg, 2017). Riedl and Harrison use stories to train an AI system which would respect human values, i.e. have a "value alignment" (Riedl & Harrison, 2016), which demonstrates the extent to which literature can be seen as a literal encoding of human values. Empathy engages our

imagination; we imagine our thoughts and emotions in another person's shoes, which can improve interpersonal relationships and contribute to better understanding of cultural and political problems, as we learn through literature to adopt different and/or conflicting perspectives on them (Bean & Moni, 2003, p. 646). Stronger empathy responses also make us more attuned to ethical concerns in various scenarios, even to those in which we have no prior experience. Thus, literature has the potential to assist students to become responsible citizens who think critically about their environment (Nikitina, 2009, p. 40) because "fiction reading leads to a small ($g=.15-.16$), but statistically significant improvement in social cognitive performance compared to nonfiction reading or no reading" (Dodell-Feder & Tamir, 2018, p. 1724). This critical awareness contributes to policy and citizen science as it makes us better leaders and citizens, in tune with conflicting interests. As an example, empathy has been shown to improve political negotiations, as it is "critical in overcoming biases, transcending long-held enmities, and increasing the likelihood of cooperation." (Holmes & Yarhi-Milo, 2017, [abstract]).

In combination with empathy and critical thinking, literary studies build textual analysis skills, "a form of diligent reading practice that does not necessarily come naturally but is built on forms of literary education and engagement that are at the heart of literature pedagogy" (Bartosch, 2021, p. 162). This skill played into Harvard English professor Elaine Scarry's involvement in discussions of aeroplane crashes. Her work "was cited on the first page of a NASA study of EMI [electromagnet inference] commissioned by T.W.A. 800 investigators," despite her having had "no formal training in aviation science" and having "never been near a crash site" (Eakin, 2000). And while her discovery was proven to be false (McKenna, 2021), she contributed a new perspective of looking and analysing an issue outside of the literary world turning "the fragmented evidentiary record" into a "seamless narrative tending inexorably towards a single conclusion" (Eakin, 2000). Scarry wanted to use literary criticism "to solve social problems and save lives," and says that "In fact, you have an increased obligation, because you know how to do research" (Eakin, 2000). Scarry encourages the application of literary analysis skills beyond the field of literary studies, and, as a result, "[t]o the literary reader, the appeal of Scarry's hypothesis is its seemingly limitless capacity for explanation" (Eakin, 2000). Adopting the perspective of a literary critic can offer novel solutions to social and cultural problems.

The perspective of a literary critic also privileges attention to style in a text, which is crucial to narrating a captivating story in journalism. In the reporting process, journalists rely on storytelling and "New Journalists" would advocate more strongly still for a focus on stylistic and rhetorical devices in their journalistic storytelling. "New Journalism...refers to a different style of journalistic writing which is based on a renewed commitment to principles of honesty and thoroughness and which encourages writers to exercise the freedom of a new subjective, creative, and candid style of reportage and commentary" (Johnson, 1971). Journalists who report facts in story form engage the reader's attention. Journalism has a "social function," and "stories have public and political significance," which can lose appeal if facts are stacked together without a connecting story or narrative (Roiland, 2015, p. 62). Knowing narrative structures and styles that capture the reader's attention helps to report while capturing the reader's personal interest and involvement. Hartsock appeals to the need of paying more attention to "literary journalism," which he uses interchangeably with "New journalism" (2009, p. 5). In times of "dramatic change" we need literary journalism because "the human mind is wired to engage in inquiry into the world by telling stories in the conventional sense of 'storytelling'" (Hartsock, 2009, p. 5). Ford claims that "[m]ore than ever today there is a need

for the literary journalist; for the writer who is sufficiently journalistic to sense the swiftly changing aspects of this dynamic era, and sufficiently literary to gather and shape his material with the eye and the hand of the artist.” (1937, p. 1). Applying a literary style when exploring social and cultural issues engages the reader and helps journalists to examine themes more independently from expectations and political restrictions.

Finding unprecedented solutions to social and cultural problems is also crucial in business leadership. Consultancies often rely on fiction and storytelling to coach business leaders. Time Kitchen, for instance, encourages people to explore and engage in exploratory thinking (Booth & Berson, n.d.) often in a fictional context. This company includes clients like “VCs, data scientists, mobility providers, shirt makers” (Booth & Berson, n.d.). In a similar way, by improving the capacity to analyse narratives and stories, literature turns us into better storytellers, which is important e.g. for marketing. Numerous consultancy firms focus on improving companies’ story, reflecting the general interest for storytelling in the business world (see e.g. The Story Mill; Consultancy.uk). Stories touch our emotions, and their emotional draw can improve sales in the industry: “Storytelling is a powerful way to connect people and engage, excite and educate them so that you can move them towards making a decision or taking a particular action” (The Story Mill, n.d.). Humanities-based and story-based business leadership is also considered to be better at engaging the customers’ interest in the company (Madsbjerg, 2017).

Consultancies and other companies can also improve intercultural communication capacities through literature. Literature teaches us profoundly about cultural identities: “literature and art are symbolic expressions of cultural identities, embodying their creator’s visions of who they were, are, or could be. These visions encompass one or more aspects of culture, such as ethnicity, geographical context, gender, and politics” (Hereniko, 1999, p. 406). Understanding cultural specificities and identities is crucial for effective business communication because it encourages inclusivity and improves work across different countries.

In the medical field, literary analysis skills can be applied in the consulting room to better treat patients. In narrative medicine (Charon, 2011), one listens to and analyses the patient’s narrative of their illness. Firstly, when the doctor takes the time to listen to the patient’s narrative, it can have a “therapeutic” effect on the patient (Charon, 2011, p. 212) and thus improve their psychological well-being. Secondly, the treating doctor can “quickly and accurately hear and interpret what a patient tries to say” (Charon, 2011, p. 211). “Narrative competence gives the doctor not only the means to understand the patient, but fresh means to understand the disease itself” (Charon, 2011, p. 211). Narrative medicine requires “a combination of textual skills (identifying a story’s structure, adopting its multiple perspectives, recognizing metaphors and allusions), creative skills (imagining many interpretations, building curiosity, inventing multiple endings), and affective skills (tolerating uncertainty as a story unfolds, entering the story’s mood)” (Charon, 2011, p. 211), which can be acquired via a literary perspective, and engagement with literary texts. Literary studies adds to the medical practice “empathy and reflection,” which is especially important for making ethical decisions (Charon, 2011, p. 212). The increasing interest in narrative medicine is demonstrated by the increase in academic clinics including narrative medicine in their approach (Gowda et al., 2019) and by research showing positive outcomes of narrative medicine, such as “high participant satisfaction and positive outcomes across various competencies” (Remein et al., 2020).

More widely in the field of medicine and psychology, literature contributes to an improvement and a better understanding of mental health. Reading fiction has been shown to have psychological benefits (Caracciolo & Van Duuren, 2015) and give meaning (Southgate, 2009, 96). It helps to “gain useful knowledge about the world in which he [the human] lives, spiritual nourishment and sense of values” (Steinberg, 1974, p. 442). Fiction is therefore crucial for sensemaking or finding meaning. Semino believes that “metaphors can be a helpful resource of talking and thinking about the experience of illness” (Semino, 2023), and on this basis developed the “Metaphor Menu” for cancer patients, to provide people with a wider vocabulary for self-expression about their condition, and help people with or without cancer to connect and empathise with the experience of living with the illness. This discursive intervention assists individuals to express themselves and to be understood in their struggle, which can also have further positive effects on their mental health generally, building a sense of agency often missing in clinical settings. Furthermore, so-called “bibliotherapy” has emerged to describe a way of selecting and ‘prescribing’ fiction, like the right drug to treat a given psychological condition. It can be applied to help patients overcome the experience of loss, grief and bereavement (Gallagher, 2020, p. 15), as carefully selected reading provides patients with words and examples by which to open up and describe their own traumatic experiences (Gallagher, 2020, p. 17).

By teaching us about human values, literature can also help us in developing better human-focussed AI systems. The reason for this lies within the fact that these systems are built upon human produced and categorised data, with the goal of ultimately interacting with humans. An example of this could be developing AI that respects ethical values, such as respecting an individual’s right to privacy, in spite of and in line with cultural differences in how this is perceived (Edmond, Yakupova, and Ketzan, 2024). The authors of this piece (and indeed of the entire collection in which it appears) position literature as an intelligent system that provides us with background understanding of wider cultural sensemaking, making us aware of issues that have already existed for a while, but have evolved and changed, or which we have been forced to revisit, e.g. with the development of AI. Literature can also be a teacher for creative AI. Sarah Atkinson’s *Charisma.ai* storytelling AI aims at realising interactive and immersive storytelling. To create well-rounded characters which the reader or player can engage with, the AI needs to learn from narrative systems (Smithies et al., 2022), which shows that literature can be used as a tool to understand and teach the human psyche.

c. Literature as a Predictive Model

Literature can function as a predictive model in two ways; first, one may look at literature of the past, uncover patterns, and thus predict future developments. This perspective will be further explored in the discussion that follows. Second, one may look at science fiction literature or speculative literature specifically to imagine, and thus predict, potential developments in the future, an approach which will be explored in section d. below: “Literature as Prototyping the Future”. Science fiction, however, can be, and often is, inspired by a (non-fictitious or fictitious) past, so the two points are often related.

Southgate states that learning from literature and literary history can help us to deal with the future (2009, 96). Wertheimer’s “Project Cassandra,” funded by the German Ministry of Defence, applies literature from the past and present to predict political conflicts (Greenfield,

2021). Wertheimer is himself a German author and former professor for modern German literature and comparative literature at the University of Tübingen. As such, he recognises literature's potential to reflect even subtle cultural tensions interacting with political ideologies, and uses literature as a model to foresee cultural and political developments.

By means of a conflict-focused text and reception analysis, a “mood picture”, an emotion map, of the respective focus region can be created. The idea behind this is to make visible the characteristics of those parameters that control conflict-tinged behaviour of groups – consciously or unconsciously. The focus is on working out socially relevant topics, the question of changing narrative structures, new identity constructions, reference stories, the analysis of reception spaces, the emotional *Befindlichkeiten* etc. In this way, the potential for violence, for example through the increased production and reception of “destructive” texts, can be recognized early on. The aim of the project is to identify these very potentials for violence at an early stage and to assess their dynamics. (Weltethos Institut, n.d.)

Wertheimer sees that “an author’s intention is both knowable and affects the way readers think and act in the real world” (Greenfield, 2021). Literary analysis can thus bring us beyond the content level of a text and uncover intentions and unconscious perceptions. The Cassandra Project analyses both ephemeral and nakedly ideological writings, and takes into account the “literary industry” of a region or country, which considers the distribution, removal, and recognition (won prizes) of novels (Greenfield, 2021), to make better predictions. The Cassandra Project has successfully predicted conflicts such as the “outbreak of hostilities in Algeria and then in Nagorno-Karabakh in 2020” (Greenfield, 2021). Despite literature’s power to predict or inspire our future, one also needs to listen to these predictions. Wertheimer points out that although we have the means to predict the future, we may still be subject to Cassandra’s curse; we do not want to listen or act to prevent foreseeable disasters (2021).

d. Literature as Prototyping the Future

This final model was inspired by Johnson’s concept of “Science Fiction Prototyping” (Johnson, 2009), which is founded upon the practice of writing science fiction stories with the intention to use this as a method by which to develop solutions for future problems. Many works and authors of science fiction or speculative fiction represent attempts to imagine potential futures based on developments observed in our past or present. Octavia Butler, for instance, keenly observed the technologies, inventions, and social issues in her environment to speculate about their potential development (Streeby, 2017, p. 72). In contrast to the models described above, however, Butler looks back in order to understand not the past or present, but the future: “Butler coined the word HistoFuturist to describe herself as a memory worker and ‘historian who extrapolates from the human past and present as well as the technological past and present’[...] Butler’s speculative archiving and imagining of worlds that were significant distortions of her present are connected and make her an important early climate change intellectual” (Streeby, 2017, p. 72). This particular applied context provides an important frame of reference for her work, as the challenges of climate change, require the application of strategic foresight (Ameel and Craps 2020; see also Bartosch 2021 on literary studies’ contribution to an affective pedagogical education to prepare students for a future with climate change). Reading and writing climate change fiction contributes to sensemaking related to these issues and to an understanding of their magnitude (Bartosch, 2021, p. 162). Understanding and predicting realistic futures helps us to prepare emotionally and practically

for them, by building resilience or indeed inspiring action to counteract crises in development (see Streeby 2017, on activism inspired by literature). Fictional spaces allow us to gain a deeper understanding of real-world crises and thereby build a resilience for our futures that extends beyond fiction (Bartosch, 2021, p. 164). The literary narrative has the “potential” to “mobilise,” it is a “catalyst” for understanding “issues on personal, communal as well as global scales,” and it serves as an “epistemic resource for engaging with scale differences as well as their complex linkages and can thus be seen as a means of turning ‘derangements of scale’ (Clark, 2012) into affordances of resilience” (Bartosch, 2021, p. 164). Reading science fiction to think about technological development and future challenges is beneficial not only for classrooms (Bartosch, 2021) but also for every citizen, as it draws our attention to issues we need to focus on, but which may seem to have no immediate urgency, such as climate change. Reading about imagined lives of future generations whose immediate problems are environmental and a consequence of our inaction can engage a speculative empathy, and therefore help to instigate action and a deeper understanding.

Science Fiction can confront the reader emotionally with future challenges and motivate them to explore solutions. Isaac Asimov, for instance, engaged in design fiction when constructing a science fiction world, in which he developed laws of robotics, far ahead of his time, which are “not without flaws,” but nevertheless “widely accepted within mainstream science as providing a well-founded moral framework for a society of robots and humans” (Chin et al., 2004, p. 15). Asimov paved the way for dealing with challenges in robots and AI far ahead of these technologies’ existence. Science fiction does not only prepare us for potential futures but also inspires and shapes these futures.

Science fiction holds significant influence over technological innovation and scientific research. For instance, Jules Verne inspired the U.S. Navy’s first submarines and the modern helicopter (Tavakoli-Far, 2013). It was Arthur C. Clarke who first proposed using satellites for global communications in 1945 (Tweney, 2011). Everything from the desire to visit “Mars to flying cars to digital drugs, robot friends to teleportation, GPS to mobile communicators, smart food to mitochondrial reproduction techniques,” has roots in science fiction (Bassett, Steinmueller, & Voss, 2013). (Zaidi, 2019, p. 16)

This process by which science fiction presents potential future technologies and thereby shapes their realisation is a “two-way pollination between prospective studies and science fiction...Science fiction, through its narratives, enables closing the gap between images of futures and necessary actions to materialize the said futures” (Pinto & Medina, 2020, p. 292). Seeing the influential power of science fiction literature on the development of our technologies, Johnson (2009) decided to turn fiction writing into an active process of design thinking; imagining future scenarios *with the purpose* to explore the potential of current scientific knowledge and technologies, as well as their potential challenges. He calls this process “Science Fiction Prototyping” (SFP). SFP is a “blending of science fiction and science fact” (Johnson, 2009). SFP distinguishes between scientific fact and fiction, but the ultimate goal is to “[p]roductively confus[e]” the two. Merging the two “may be the only way for the science of fact to reach beyond itself and achieve more than incremental forms of innovation” (Johnson, 2009). SFP “leads to the creation of detailed concepts about what seems uncertain, with the objective of making it possible for planners, public policy managers, and project managers to use them routinely” (Pinto & Medina, 2020, p. 292). Interviews with AI researchers in the UK showed the impact of science fiction reading on their career choice,

ideas, ethical thinking, and more (Dillon & Schaffer-Goddard, 2023). Now some institutions, including MIT (MIT Media Lab, 2020), offer SFP to envision future scenarios in the classroom.

Science fiction can also be an effective tool to teach students “Creative Anticipatory Ethical Reasoning” (York & Conley, 2020, p. 2985) in the classroom. In York and Conley’s experiment, science fiction stories helped the students to better understand and empathise with various groups in our technological futures, such as in which way autonomous cars can help people with mobility issues. They showed that students can better grasp abstract future concepts through design fiction, for which they included examples from literature, such as teaching Philosophy of Science with Chiang’s “Division by Zero” (2002) or teaching “The Philosophy of Technology” with Cline’s *Ready Player One* (2011). To develop the student’s capacity for empathy, ethical reasoning and foresight, stories and fiction are often used in education to make complicated concepts or data intelligible.

2.3 Concluding remarks on Applied Literary Studies

It is important to clarify that the four categories described above are not in all cases being consciously deployed by the authors and practitioners of the projects and work described. They were developed instead as a part of the preparatory research for the CLS INFRA interviews, as an instrument through which to communicate the trends we identified in the highly diverse body of research we were able to assemble that reflected applied approaches to literary studies. Although the categories cannot be strictly delineated, with many examples of practice falling between or across them, they nonetheless provide a useful structure by which to introduce the concept of and potential use cases for applied literary studies to an audience that may not recognise these possibilities. With this caveat in place, we can view the relationship between the categories as follows:

	Past	Present	Future
Build Individual Capacity		Literature as Capacity Building	
Enhance Collective Intelligence	Literature as Evidence	Literature as Predictive Model	Literature as Prototype

Figure 1. The four ALS models identified according to their scope and temporality

This separation into axes of temporality and scope brings us back to the original questions of the place of computation methods as a potential contributor to applied approaches in literary

studies. Computational approaches to literary studies, as opposed to traditional literary studies, enable us to pose new research questions involving more data and thus opens doors to new potential uses of literature. “[C]orpus-related techniques allow one’s analysis to (1) encompass more than one could possibly encompass with reasonable human labor, and (2) be systematic, and (3) be fine-grained,...[CLS can] make explicit things that readers are only dimly aware of, if at all” (Hoover, et al., 2014, p. 30). In this context, CLS tools can, for example, help to map common concerns in science fiction literature and shift our focus to issues around sustainability in our technology and environment. Another possible way is to explore the style of AI imaginaries, i.e. do we envision robots to use the same language as humans or would it be, for example, devoid of emotions or even moral judgement? CLS tools can uncover these subtleties in a large corpus and display the things we need to focus on now for better and sustainable future visions. These examples all fall under the categories of collective intelligence, past present and future. What CLS may not be able to do as well as a traditional close reading approach, however, is likely to fall within the category of individual capacity building, where an individual’s journey through a linear narrative may be the most important aspect of the method.

As a final note, although this was not the primary aim of the research undertaken, one further interesting finding from this research is the degree to which Applied Literary Studies appears as a methodology not in literary studies itself, but in other disciplines. Geography, History, Management Studies, and Design research were all represented in our corpus, and while many of the authors may have at some point in their career studied literature, the knowledge they were creating seemed only to draw from, at an often superficial level, but not necessarily feed back in to, literary studies as a form of basic research. This wider question of where applied research might sit in the wider field of literary studies is beyond the scope of this study, but raises significant questions for work engaging this topic in the future.

3. Interviews

3.1 Introduction

The research review and consolidation addressing the concept of Applied Literary Studies was carried out as an essential enabler in the exploration of how infrastructure for computational literary studies might be used by practitioners from beyond the circles of professional and literary research. It provided a fundamental support for the CLS INFRA project in its aim to envision an infrastructure that can contribute to the work of various professions beyond academia. Leveraging the opportunity to maximise the use and impact of the infrastructure would be a key driver for sustainability, but also for an optimal ecosystem of knowledge generation and transfer in a humanities field, examples of which are difficult, if not impossible, to point to. In developing our interview questions and framework, we adapted elements of both the focussed interview (Merton & Kendall, 1946) technique and that of the narrative interview (Horsdal, 2016). In this way we felt we could maximise the benefit of our preparatory research into how we might describe current trends in the application of literary studies, while also being open to the nuances of the professional ‘life stories’ that the practitioners we would interview, whom we had identified as likely to be at least tacitly incorporating an awareness of literature into their work, had to tell.

Based on our research around applications of literature, fictional narratives, and storytelling, we developed a set of target sectors that could comprise potential user groups for infrastructure for literary analysis from beyond the academic sphere. These sectors included the following: journalism, publishing, consultancy, and policy. In the course of recruiting for and carrying out the interviews, we added two additional sectors, namely medicine/psychology (bibliotherapy), and artistic practice. Ultimately, we carried out 15 interviews with 2 or 3 individuals representing each of these fields, with the ultimate goal of being able to use their accounts as user scenarios (descriptions in their own words of a real or imagined research task) from which we would be able to develop more structured user stories (see section 4 below). The research plan received ethical approval from the Trinity College Dublin School of Languages, Literatures and Cultural Studies Research and Ethics Committee in November of 2022 and the interviews were carried out jointly by the authors of this report between February and May 2023. The transcripts of these interviews are available as open research data for research reuse purposes, and can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/records/12784256>

A semi-structured narrative interview style was chosen as the most suitable for the goals of the research. This format helped us to be open to individual user requirements and professional environments, while following a structure to compare the uses of literature in those varying environments. This interview style helped us to work around the challenge of contextualising an interview with a double-hypothetical starting point (“if such an infrastructure existed, how would you use it?”), and also enabled us to work together with professionals to envision potential uses of literature or a CLS toolbox in their work. The main challenge in the conversations with the participants was that some of the CLS tools we wanted to introduce are not technically mature enough to be used by non-researchers as seamlessly as we might have to describe it. Nevertheless, this would ultimately provide useful input for the project as a whole, as an infrastructure seeking to widen its user base needs to understand the demands and potential use case scenarios in and beyond its current remit, so as to lay the groundwork for the development of user friendly, useful, accessible tools, and sustainable tools.

Another challenge we were required to navigate was the imprecise and often terminologically overlapping usage of related concepts such as “literature,” “fiction,” “narratives,” and “stories/storytelling”. Although these terms may have very distinctive meanings within literary scholarship, we quickly realised that those shadings of context and granularity were not as assiduously protected outside of scholarship. This realisation motivated us to expand our own semantic field, to be inclusive of narratives and storytelling, to encourage our participants to think as openly and creatively as we wanted them to, so they could envision an infrastructure that might work for them. That said, we also need to be sensitive in interpreting the accounts we collected, that not every affordance ascribed by the interviewees to stories in a generic sense could be met by literature in specific. Indeed, many participants seemed more receptive and open to speaking about the role of narratives or stories, as opposed to literature and fiction. Further terms we encountered included anecdotes (int 3), personal accounts (int 3, int 9), or historical texts (e.g. int 6), and often, participants discussed theatre and film as well.

The interviews proceeded as follows: we first prompted the interview subject to tell us about their role and uses of fiction/ narrative/ storytelling in their sector that they were aware of. We then described and presented examples of the four models we had found being used within applied literature and asked for their opinions on these models. We also asked whether they could see themselves using fiction in each way, whether they had already used it in their work,

and whether they saw any dangers in using literature in that way. Lastly, we asked about data mining and computational tools, and whether they could see themselves using a CLS toolbox for their work. What follows below is a description of how each of the four models of applied literary studies was received, as well as some of the challenges and concerns raised by the interviewees.

a. Interviewees' Consideration of Literature as Evidence of the Past and Present

To present this model to our interviewees, we chose to feature as an example Westphal's chapter on how various narratives by travellers, immigrants, and indigenous people provided a multi-perspectival view to reconstruct the city of Tangier (Westphal, 2011, p. 128). In general, all participants found that the mentioned examples could be a fruitful way to inform geography and history. A few participants, particularly from journalism and policymaking (int 6 and int 3, int 9), while open to the idea, however, saw themselves using historical texts more than fictional texts for this case, even if they had access to selected corpora.

Policymakers suggested using literature to back up arguments in policy formation or in the communication of policies being introduced. One participant, for instance, mentioned that many Irish politicians would not know much about life on the Irish islands: "I've never set foot on an offshore island [...] and there I was, sitting in government buildings, with no knowledge of it at all" (int 1). Literature could be a way of bridging this kind of knowledge gap. The participants believed that literature written by people who had either lived on the islands or visited them could give better insight than statistics into emotional and historical tensions. "And somebody said to me, we need a strategy. So where did I go? Well, I went back to literature, I went back to what makes these islands distinct" (int 1). Similarly, another participant from the policy group, who worked on political strategies for Northern Ireland, said that they would go back to personal and historical narratives from Northern Ireland to better understand the tensions between various interest groups.

I suppose that people are most likely to encounter narratives through specific cases. They're going to want to read a book about something. They want to be struck by a poem about something or by a play. I should mention then the importance of cinema and theatre, of course, as well.[...] It can help shape views of history, of communities and so on. (int 3)

These stories were felt to help to bring greater emotional impact to communications with the public, as well as to other policymakers who would have to make decisions that would have an impact on people's lives beyond their personal social circle, into which they might introduce their own unconscious biases. While the strongest emotional impact was still felt to come from a close reading of these narratives and fictions, the policy-makers among our participants showed an interest in the potential of deriving information from literary corpora e.g. through word clouds, sentiment analysis, topic modelling, etc. For instance, if they were to approach a corpus of literature from the islands or Northern Ireland with CLS tools, this might enable them to uncover prevalent topics or tensions in regions relevant to their strategies.

Participants from policymaking often referred back to the importance of personal stories and accounts, be they factual or fictional. In conjunction with a CLS tool that would help them query a corpus of personal accounts, they would see it potentially being applied in passport offices (int 3) or to be aware of different experiences that people go through during the development of strategies (int 1 and int 9). With the addition of personal stories, the management of the cases could be better adapted to various immigrant groups with the addition of personal stories. “[R]unning the passport office—over a million applications a year for passports. And it might be, I suppose, if you could delve more deeply into the exact timing of applications, into the ages of those who apply in time and those who apply late, or if there’s a regional dimension—all of that could potentially be useful.” (int 3). This awareness and knowledge might help to ensure that the government could better respond to its citizens’ needs. An example of this offered by one of the interviewees was the “Life Events” project (int 9, Citizens Information), an initiative for policymakers to help them better understand their citizen’s stories. Life Events consists of a database representing “situations that occur which result in a series of transactions between an individual and various public sector organisations in Ireland, for example having a baby or getting married. These documents provide a short guide to all the information you may need, to help guide you through these events.” (Citizens Information).

The ability to go through a larger corpus of personal accounts and texts could help policymakers to shed light on underrepresented and initially understudied experiences, such as experiences of women in mother and baby homes or of women having to deal with sexual abuse in the military; “If you look at something like that tragic inquiry that’s going to have to start in the Defence Forces at the minute, or you look at mother and baby homes, or any of those, the cervical cancer issue, what has happened culturally, and I guess the Northern Ireland Troubles, actually, is another very good example where increasingly part of the data set is the stories” (int 9). In the “Life Events” project:

long term, we’re going to end up creating new value data sets, which will actually add something going forward because somebody who’s been Irish for generation upon generation upon generation instinctively knows how you get a driving licence. But if you’re first generation or second, you don’t even know possibly that the RSA exists. So it is trying to be more inclusive in terms of how government services are provided. [...] We’re actually asking the person getting the story, understanding the journey. That’s starting to apply in other areas as well as to how we do get better at policymaking from it[...] what we’re starting to see is that stories do become a key part of policy formation. But that’s almost happened in the last few years by accident rather than design. (int 9)

Numbers-based statistics were not considered by policymakers to be sufficient to represent suffering and the real, lived concerns of the public (int 3, int 9), a lack that can be addressed via the qualitative evidence held in stories. Consultancy companies, it seems, would perceive literature and narrative in a similar way. As an example, one participant related how they would use literature to learn about the history of a complex phenomenon, such as electrification (int 4). While they would draw more from historical records to learn about the chronology of events, they would go into fiction to better understand people’s behaviour and emotional reactions to technological changes. Fiction would allow them to more richly advise tech companies on what reactions and behaviour could be expected from people facing new technologies, such as during the implementation of AI tools. Fictional narrative thus animates

us to think about the consequences of technology on society. “I use those stories, I’ve done a lot of work here to get people to think about the positive and negative consequences of technology” (int 4). Nevertheless, despite the desire to implement more literature into their work, at least one participant from consultancy voiced a perception that it was currently challenging to navigate a large corpus:

I think there’s a signposting problem because there’s so much literature in the world to even know when and where to look. It’s not just an easy search for a title or keyword search, noun association. If I wanted to know more about this, and I was open to literary sources as well as other ones, where would I start that kind of signposting to something?
(int 4)

In the mind of this participant, who was very open towards CLS tools, a tool that could visualise patterns in textual data, giving a better overview and making more comprehensible the navigation of larger corpora could bridge that gap and turn literature into a useful resource, which they would see as adding value into their work: fiction “as a way to understand or provide an expression of place [...] could give you a sense of it far quicker than any other way because of the system how it’s expressed” and “it will get you to a sense of place much quicker than anything else” (int 4).

Literature, in particular personal stories of the past and present are also key to understanding illness. Literature can validate experiences of illness and help us understand and research them. Research on psychiatric diseases has gone hand in hand with literature, especially autobiographical writing, because they can represent the language, perspective, and experience of patients with a psychiatric condition, as well as how it affects people close to them. Examples of this are studies on e.g. schizophrenia in *Henry’s Demons* or autism in *The Speed of Dark*, *The Language of Others*, and *A Curious Incident of the Dog in the Night-Time* (int 5). Nowadays storytelling and personal accounts extend into the technological space, such as online fora. One participant related their experience of looking at fora and articles commenting on the description of a person’s perspective with mental illness, and observing how it helped people with that illness to feel validated. “Especially people who have experiences that might be taboo, or if you read the story written by somebody who has a similar experience, it can be really validating and useful in all sorts of ways” (int 5). Research informed by literature that looks at the language people use when suffering from a disease, combining literary language and disease to look into metaphors that cancer patients use, was named an inspiration to one of the interviewees (int 5). People affected by physical diseases, such as cancer, adopt a language that is particular to their experience, and thus share almost a cultural sphere of their own.

Participants from publishing saw potential in using literature as evidence for other fields like history and geocriticism, but they did not see many applications in their own field like e.g. using literature as evidence to know what genre a demographic is interested in, in order to adapt the publishing process into that direction. Firstly, from a value perspective, they believed that it is important to maintain authenticity of the literary production instead of fitting the market; “there’s a danger that people will start to write texts in order to fit into [the market]” (int 7). From a practical perspective, the publishing process was also perceived as taking too long to adapt to user interest. One participant from this group explained this with the example of Stieg Larsson’s popularity and “Scandi Crime”:

So Stieg Larsson started selling really well[...] Then the second one comes out and flies, and you go, okay, there's this thing called "scandi crime" that appears to be a thing, so let's see if we can get ourselves some of that, right? So let's say by the time the second book comes out, we're alert that this is a thing, and then we go out looking for authors and say, it takes us six months to find someone who could write something good in that space. Publishing timelines for something like that, 18 months to two years. By the time our book one hits the stage, the trend is four years old, the wave has broken. [...] But if you try to ride a wave that's already there, you are too late. (int 11)

They would, however, consult consumer data on databases like Nielsen (int 11) or try and consult someone on whether certain content could be sold in a certain country from a cultural point of view, e.g. selling novels about gay characters could be problematic in some countries in Eastern Europe (int 11); "When I talk to an agent or a publisher from Eastern Europe, I give them a content warning. I say, 'this book contains gay characters.' For some of them, they go, 'great.' And for some of them, they go, 'I'm sorry, I can't sell that in my country.'" (int 11).

One of the participants from publishing related their experience of editing submitted works, and in this context of this activity they felt perhaps they could profit from CLS tools to identify stylistic features or to do keyword searches to identify sections which might benefit from improvement. "I don't know if that's the name for it, but it's like a word search. But instead of using just one word, you can put in groups of two words or three words or four words or five words or however many words you want. So you can see if a writer has a tick" (int 7). They would use the results from this kind of stylometric analysis to points to the sections that might need to be improved in the submitted texts, e.g. a tick in the author's speech.

Interviewees from the field of art did also relate to the concept of literature as evidence, for example where they would create projects that require better knowledge of a topic. "So years ago we did a piece called 'The Stoneybatter River Walk,' where we would have compiled a lot of research on the area of Stoneybatter and Smithfield, such as legends, folk stories, geographical phenomenon, other ideas, probably just like loose ideas" (int 14). More than the role of evidence, however, literature plays the role of inspiration to artists, which we discuss in the next section on literature as a mode of individual capacity building.

b. Interviewees' Consideration of Literature as Capacity Building

Although widely validated by our interviewees, whether we truly improve our empathy or storytelling skill with every novel that we read is difficult to measure because those capabilities are not developed through reading alone. A policy maker commented on this:

I don't think that future leaders are obliged to take modules in which you have a range of different literary sources. But I think that those leaders who do read have a greater depth of awareness and sense of the background. However, while I would be surprised if Bertie Ahern, for example, had ever read a work of fiction in his life, it didn't stop him from being an extraordinarily effective leader when it came to Northern Ireland. But I think, in general, people have this sort of a deeper sense of things, and maybe, in some cases, a greater empathy with others through literature. (int 3)

Just like this policymaker, all participants we asked seemed to believe that reading literature affects people in a positive way, developing that “greater depth of awareness and sense of background” (int 3). Some policymakers also believe that literature improves an individual’s capacity in political decision-making (int 1, int 9). However, due to the difficulty of measuring to what extent literature contributed to the given capacities, participants were hesitant to fully agree with the model because they could only rely on a personal sense or belief that literature contributes to these capacities. Another policymaker expressed this difficulty as follows:

And I’m thinking particularly about my colleagues in foreign affairs who would definitely have drawn on fictional stories[..]They are always reaching back into literature. [Colleague name] is actually a scholar of English literature, he has published a book on Ulysses. So ‘yes’ must be the answer. I read extensively. But I just regard it as part of who I am, as a part of what I do. It’s intrinsic, it is who I am. I read, but that’s not the case with all my colleagues. So I don’t know, I don’t know the answer to that. But I do think it’s leadership and empathy and getting decisions made and getting agreement. (int 1)

Beyond the challenge of measuring the correlation between the consumption of literature and increased capacities, another difficulty with this premise lies in the chicken or egg question: are people who read more literature more empathetic or are people who are inherently more empathetic drawn to reading literature because they can get more out of these stories and engaging emotional journeys, as per the interviewee who stated that: “I just regard it as part of who I am, as a part of what I do” (int 1). A participant from publishing firmly believed that literature and fictional stories can develop capacities such as emotional intelligence by offering us character models which develop our moral compass:

Do I think reading fiction makes for a better human being? I do, yeah. [...]My daughter was just asked to write an essay on emotional intelligence, which she’s been doing over the last couple of days[...]I said, ‘well, why don’t you take the characters from those fictions [e.g. Aladdin] and explore emotional intelligence from their perspective?’ So the genie has it, Aladdin finally gets there, but Jafar forgets it. So it allows you to see good behaviour and bad behaviour modelled in ways that aren’t harmful to people. So, yeah, why not in a professional context as well? (int 11).

Participants from consultancy and bibliotherapy related having already used literature and its archetypes to deal with personal and interpersonal challenges, which is also a way of developing emotional intelligence. A participant from a consultancy company mentioned a colleague’s work using Vonnegut’s archetypes of stories to explain why collaborations among work groups commonly succeeded or failed. Based on those archetypes and the understanding of which archetypes the work groups fell under, the team was able to come up with better solutions for their conflicts (int 4). For those groups, understanding archetypes of stories that they fell under, provided them with a new perspective that led to different, and often better, solutions to their issues in collaborating. Yet even in this case the connection was not felt to be clear cut:

But not all the collaborations worked, and that’s because collaborations are people who talk about trust and alignment, but actually when you get into the weeds and all, they’re just really difficult, and it erupts the doubts, and when we actually analysed the data we realised they were falling into these archetypes of these stories[...] it has proven to be a

very powerful way to talk about collaborations, to get people to think about their own collaborations and go, 'oh yes, I can see I'm in this story. How do I stop this so I can go on a more positive trajectory and what is needed?' So there's a very powerful way to get people not just for us to express the data that was quite subjective and quite qualitative, but actually then get people to connect and see how they might use those outputs (int 4).

Another participant who draws on archetypes from folktales to achieve therapeutic outcome in patients (int 10) chooses the material she does largely because:

the language is simple. They use the rule of three in repetition, which is almost universal and must have something to do with the way the human brain processes things. They use lovely archetypes. Archetypes are really helpful.[...]the imagery, it descends into the brain and is simulated very quickly, and people relate to it, perhaps even from a personal experience from many, many years ago, (int 10).

Or when treating addictions, "that ability to tell a story is extremely empowering for people. It will help them to be agents in their own health" (int 10). The bibliotherapist emphasises the therapeutic value of literature, that working with it can improve well-being by building necessary mental skills for resilience, or as they said, "we need to use story in a way that we can allow ourselves a hopeful story of the future" (int 10). Similarly, another participant said that they would see themselves benefitting from a CLS tool that could function as a coach and recommendation system picking the right books to deal with stress or grief:

There was something I saw once that I wish existed more, where someone had suggested [...] how to use fictional stories to help you with whatever mindset you were in or when you're experiencing stress, grief, whatever it was, [...] If you could go, put it into a system, and that system would suggest to you five books you should read.[...]It was like the fictional, literary, self-help version of, 'if you are experiencing X, that's interesting.' And it feels like a very individual journey. Literature as a coach almost or literature as a mentor. (int 4)

The way literature describes human behaviour in a fictional environment, helps people to look for solutions beyond their immediate perspectives and personal interests on a more global scale in a pressure-free environment, like a thought experiment in which problem-solving has no real-life repercussions. Fictional stories can provide a thought experiment for common emotional struggles and how to deal with them. The example of a book recommendation system for mental struggles could in theory be exactly the kind of service that might be built and developed with the help of CLS tools, albeit in a highly interdisciplinary context.

In the literature review, we found evidence that many consultancy companies use stories to teach leadership. One participant from consultancy confirmed that literature, especially if CLS tools would allow them to do explorative research on large corpora, could contribute to their work with clients. "I would love an opportunity to do a distant reading, a corpus exploration on the commercial end" (int 2). For leadership, politicians also have to rely on stories to sway the public; "it's surprising to the extent to which politicians as well, and even civil servants perhaps, do rely quite heavily on stories and narratives" (int 3)³. CLS tools could help with that

³ Which has its dangers as addressed in the "Health Warnings and Concerns" section below.

by identifying common topics, metaphors, imagery, stylistic-, and stylometric features. In policy, however, these should be used with caution, as “compelling stories can at times be at odds with the broader picture as deduced from facts, from analysis, and from deeper research” (int 3), and they can be used to divide and polarise groups of people.

While we suggested in the literature review that journalists could also profit from storytelling that engaged the use of literature, in reality, a significant constraint mitigating against this could be the fact that most journalists work in a highly pressured environment, similar to policymakers, which does not always give them the freedom to explore “literary journalism” (Hartsock, 2009, p. 5) or journalism that foregrounds style and not merely the plot.

Finally, our artists participants also saw themselves as benefiting from explorative research with CLS tools or a digital library to inspire ideas for creative projects. While this may not be building a capacity per se, analysable literary corpora certainly offer more input to work creatively. “[Wh]en I’m starting to research something, I’ll go to the bookshelf at home and just pick things. Probably there’s something that’s stuck in my mind from some point in time that has created a link. And that’s the way I’ll start assembling research and read really widely and make associations” (int 14). Another artist related working in a similar way, building a creative project starting from a prompt. “I type in what I would commonly think something was called—I’m always wrong, but I try—and I’ll eventually get to what I’m looking for.[...]So if there was some way that you could help finding or identifying those within other, fictions papers, for example, or all of those things, that would be quite useful” (int 15).

c. Interviewees’ Consideration of Literature as a Predictive Model

We presented this model with the example of Wertheimer’s “Cassandra Project” (Weltethos Institut, n.d.). More than other models, this one evoked hesitancy and criticism in the interview participants, with three out of the fifteen participants being against using literature in this way and four expressing themselves as not sure of it.

A participant from policymaking said that “[f]rom a practical policy point of view, I don’t think there’s a great deal of use or relevance” (int 3). Participants from consultancy and journalism said that it is a “trickier” (int 4) or a “flawed approach” (int 6). Even the participants who saw use in the model, felt like it should be used with “a healthy dose of scepticism” or “caution” (e.g. int 8). The things they felt were important to keep in mind, among others, were firstly, the biases and representation in the corpus and the interpretation of it, and secondly, the need to avoid oversimplifying and instrumentalising the literary production market (int 7 and int 8); “it comes back to which books you use. If we just took a certain sector of Irish society, we’re not going to get necessarily the full picture, but especially if we start to take into account that kind of representation, et cetera, I see there’s problems with who has access to being published, et cetera, et cetera” (int 8). The greatest concern was around the instrumentalisation of literature within this model (“there is a danger that the writing becomes for the market” (int 7), “the fear of it becoming too reductive or catchy” (int 8)). A participant from an art practice background said that it may be “worth asking the questions” (int 14), but they were hesitant of it being a military-funded project because it involved national and diplomatic biases. The artist also saw difficulties in the application, namely the best practices around dealing with the knowledge from literature in a policy environment; “I guess my struggle with it is; what are you doing with it after you found out? Could it possibly be used to heighten a conflict? There’s diplomacy so

you're always trying to do the dance of 'should we not say anything at this time? Because we might spur something into being, whereas if we didn't poke at it, we might not have released the energy'" (int 14). However, another participant concluded that "with all those health warnings, I think it's a worthy experiment," and added:

I do think literature has that, and maybe it's because I spent so long on this podcast, and one of our big things is about the importance of imagination. I think that's what literature does far better than the politicians, the economists, and business trends. So I think especially if something can be used in that world of interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, as one element in it, that I think is a really good way of doing it[...]we're not good at predicting the future. So I don't see a problem putting in literature to see if it actually makes us better at it. And I think particularly when you talk about that clash of culture[...]Who is documenting culture better? (int 8)

Hence, while some participants found acting on predictions based on literature problematic, the knowledge of it could enrich understanding of certain tensions, especially in the policy sphere for policymakers (e.g. int 1) and for journalists (int 12).

Most examples participants mentioned in relation to their experience or conceptualisation of literature as a predictive model bordered on the model of literature as prototyping the future. A journalist, for instance, said that they are

...absolutely fascinated [...] how some novelists or writers are able to write about things that haven't happened or attitudes that don't exist, and they're able to see an attitude that might exist and speculate on it. Then somehow one ends up with that that attitude exists. [...]You do have your Philip K. Dick or your Arthur C. Clarke, but I was also thinking about Sally Rooney, somebody like that, whose work suddenly becomes a template, and everybody begins writing like that, and it has a sort of gravitational pull. Which kind of is predictive in a way, but it's gravity that is the prediction. [...]It's predictive in that, in a boring sense, I suppose, it's trend-setting, and people begin to follow that. But in literature, it feels more important than a trend because that humanistic idea of novels, where we're actually growing our own subjectivity by reading, the fact that somebody is shaping many people's subjectivity through what they write is completely fascinating. (int 12)

This participant shifts the focus of the model of literature as a predictive model by highlighting how powerful works of literature predict the future by actually shaping it, an idea that coincides with the model of "Literature as Prototyping the Future" and interlinks the two models.

d. Interviewees' Consideration of Literature as Prototyping the Future

The question of whether literature predicts the future or in some cases actually instigates particular developments by priming the imaginaries of the future is, it seems, only separated by a fine line, yet many participants were more comfortable with the latter model. Using literature and fiction (-al scenarios) to prototype and imagine the future can figure across professions that try to think critically about e.g. current and future developments of technology. As an example for this model, we named a few inventions that we found came originally from science fiction literature, such as submarines and helicopters, and we presented Johnson's

idea of Science Fiction Prototyping (Johnson, 2009). In general, the participants responded positively to this model (13 out of the 15 participants) and nearly every participant thought of their own example of literature or a futures institute focusing on fictions to prototype the future.

One of the journalists we interviewed focusses much of their work specifically on technology, and from this standpoint, they noted how science fiction shapes our language and imagination about technology (int 13). As an example, the participant explained that early computers had flashing lights because that was the way they were represented in science fiction literature and movies (int 13). Another journalist related a similar understanding, saying that the automatic sliding doors were inspired by Star Trek. Science fiction literature provides us with a language to talk about and understand new technology, like in the case of Meta adopting their name from Neil Stephenson's novel *Snow Crash* and its description of the "metaverse" (int 2). Knowing the language around technology as described in literature helps to build a rapport, a common cultural background with the readers or listeners, that involves them with a story. "[I]t might only be imagining something five or ten years out, which I think is quite interesting as a fictional move, rather than thinking that it has to be 500 or 3000 years in the future that you can actually get something that allows you to explore really challenging subjects and in a quite transformed world" (int 13).

In the medical field, this imaginative thinking in fiction confronts us with ethical concerns of developments in medicine. The interview participant from the field of medical humanities worked with their colleagues on a project considering the dangers of new technologies around human reproduction and artificial births. This research project, called "The Future of Human Reproduction," also included on its team an expert in literature, who considered the issue from the perspective of fictional narratives. Long before our technology allowed us to think about pregnancies outside of the body, literature addressed the ethical issues and implications of this in novels like *Frankenstein*, *The Growing Season*, or *Brave New World*.

I think fiction, especially the novel, both with the short story, really allow for a full exploration because, of course, we can sit here and think through and obviously, there are people who work in different kinds of ethics from different perspectives, whose job it is to work out the implications, never mind the legal implications. (int 5)

Literature allows us to empathise with various perspectives that might be ascribed to future generations to understand the ethical concerns of a new technology. Literature can tackle ethical dilemmas that we have not yet had to address in contemporary legal and political contexts, because it imagines worlds beyond the ones we know. It is not constrained to the limitations of reality and can therefore reconfigure both the conditions of our world, and our perceptions of our place and responsibilities within it.

As mentioned in the literature review, science fiction literature prompts us to think about the consequences of our actions, such as escalation of conflict or climate change (e.g. Ameen & Craps, 2020). Literature and film can serve as a delivery mechanism for cautionary tales to make policymakers and the public more aware of the impact of certain issues. For example, "in the 1980s, when there was great fear about the danger of nuclear escalation and war, there were a couple of films which were shown in—British films, I remember in particular, but I'm sure there were others elsewhere—which purported to show the effects of a nuclear war. And those were extremely powerful and directly helped shape public opinion" (int 3). Similarly,

stories and narratives help us to reconnect with a former relationship to nature as well as our responsibility towards preserving our planet.

I'm interested in going back to find what we knew and then bringing it forward and having it in the future. So things like climate change is very relevant for it.[...]And I've used some of the indigenous wisdom poems and literature. Actually, I've read from it, and some of it was fictional, some of it was a first-person account. So that was more about imagining how we could be rather than a technological prototyping. A social prototyping perhaps (int 10).

Participants from various groups thought of examples fitting the context of science fiction prototyping, in which they did not draw so much on science fiction literature, but on concepts from Science Fiction Prototyping in an interactive, almost theatrical, way. For the example of climate change, an artist, who is also active in the political sphere, remembered an example from Japan where people from current generations role-play conversations with future generations to understand their perspective and needs in order to make more sustainable decisions (e.g. Saijo, 2022). This technique could be useful for policymakers. "One of the things we're missing in the Irish context, in my view, is a focus on the future [...] If you like, as a systematic piece of our toolkit. Other countries have this scenario-planning, forecasting, imagining the futures [...] really using imagination. I think there is potential in that, but the public policy system would need a lot of convincing" (int 1). For participants from consultancy this was also important when considering the impact of new technologies. For instance, one consultancy organised a role-play workshop simulating a customer's conversation to an AI chatbot that was soon to be implemented into another company. This turned out to be a "very useful prototyping tool" that allowed them to go "problem hunting in the future" (int 4). An artist who had been involved in design thinking and urban planning projects said that engaging with fictional worlds was crucial for imaginative thinking;

I've been on projects where you ask people what they want in the new park, and they're so bound, you have to spend so much time breaking them out of the mould of what is possible. It's not just a new swing set, this is something that could be radically transformed. And you have to do a lot of fiction work to bring the audience into something that would be far more desirable. So that's also a way, I think, that could play across different sectors (int 15).

This artist often inspires themselves with satire books to develop humorous interactive scenarios for audiences to explore challenges of technological and societal developments. These scenarios take problems out of the technological sphere into a physical space with humorous elements to expand the audience's imagination. Similarly, literature can give additional inspiration as to what issues and perspectives should be considered, offering insight into a wider variety of perspectives than just our own, inspiring newly framed dialogues regarding future problems and their impact on different societies.

3.2 Challenges and Concerns

Although our interview participants generally validated our assumption that literary studies could have a place in the work of these sectors, a number of concerns and limitations were raised in the course of our discussions. The main concerns of participants in using literature in

those ways, as already addressed in the discussion above regarding literature as a predictive model, is that these applications could lead to an instrumentalisation of literature. An editor illustrated this concern with the example of Moroccan rug production:

When they started selling Moroccan rugs, and when people started buying them, they were rugs that were made in Morocco for Moroccans, and then traders came and took them and sold them. And then when this started happening, the rug makers started to produce rugs for that market rather than them being authentic. So I think there's a danger that the writing becomes for the market. (int 7)

The concern is that perverse incentives would arise to produce literature for particular applications, a trend that would ultimately constrain the capacity of literature to function as an intelligent system. A journalist also addressed this concern, stating that:

it's just that fear of it becoming too reductive or too catchy, such as 'literature can do this, and this is what literature is for.' [...] It's that fear when you take anything, you don't want it to become 'literature will save the world', but I think it is important to be there, and it needs to be part of it. But I think you're putting too much pressure on literature, first of all, but also not recognising the complexity of why people write, isn't it? But if you start to do that, then it's where those health warnings come in. (int 8)

The same participant said that if an awareness of these dangers of simplifying and instrumentalising literature is kept in mind, these applications can be beneficial to the future of many professional fields; "But I think if you take it with all that amazing work that has already been done to really do it as a sophisticated study, then it could be something incredibly powerful that really does help us deal with tomorrow in a way better than before." (int 8).

On the other extreme from instrumentalizing literature is the challenge of forcing literature into fields beyond academia when it does not have any practical purpose at all. A consultant, for instance, said that "[t]he hesitation is probably because I would love to get it in more, but it feels like, sometimes, I'm just trying to get and wedge it in. And that's absolutely not what I would want to do. It would actually be doing the entire field a disservice because then people are like, 'well, that wasn't useful. Why are you doing that?'" (int 4). In promoting the potential of literature as an applied field, priority should be to find a balance, to meet the users' requirements in a sensitive and contextual manner, while not being overly reductive about literature's potential or role.

Furthermore, certain applications of storytelling and literature were perceived to have the potential to lead to the abuse of its power. A policymaker (int 3), among other participants (e.g. int 4), acknowledged the power of stories to sway people, which could be used to back up the delivery of policy decisions, but could also be abused:

compelling stories can at times be at odds with the broader picture as deduced from facts, from analysis, from deeper research. And people can be swayed quite easily. And I say it's the general public, yes. But it's surprising to the extent to which politicians as well, and even civil servants perhaps, do rely quite heavily on stories and narratives. (int 3)

Another, related, concern addressed the possibility of how literary evidence would interact with biases and individual agendas being promoted. Regarding the Cassandra project and using literature as a predictive model one participant said: “Depends who’s doing it, doesn’t it? And for what end? I mean, a military thing sounds a bit disturbing because they have a bias. And are they able to see past that, or are they going to see what they want to see?” (int 14).

If these health warnings are kept in mind, most participants agreed that these applications of literature could enrich their work.

4. Extracted User Stories

4.1 User stories table

The following table summarises the needs expressed by professionals in the interviews and contextualises them in a CLS context. These include CLS tools that would facilitate using literature to inform their field (e.g. int 1) or to do explorative research (e.g. int 2, int 14). The table indicates for each interview the profession of the interviewee, what tool the said, described or implied would help work in their field and what their aim might be with such a tool. The last column suggests what existing tools being used in the field of CLS could facilitate that need. Except for participant in interview 11, every participant expressed a positive sense of the potential for CLS to enrich their work if it was accessible and easy to use.

	The participant could use (something)	So that (benefit)
Artists		
Int. 14	A tool that would help explore fiction and look up metaphors, images, or particular words.	The participant can seek additional inspiration, and do associative research with more texts.
Reference to Source	“when I’m starting to research something, I’ll go to the bookshelf at home and just pick things. Probably there’s something that’s stuck in my mind from some point in time that has created a link. And that’s the way I’ll start assembling research and read really widely and make associations”	
Int. 15	A tool that would help to do research, find metaphors, analogies, look for words in fiction and their associations or collocations from a starting query.	To design interactive exhibitions to have a wider audience reflect on the implications of technology.
Reference to Source	“I type in what I would commonly think something was called—I’m always wrong, but I try—and I’ll eventually get to what I’m looking for.[...] So if there was some way that you could help finding or identifying those within other, fiction, papers, for example, or all of those things, that would be quite useful.”	
Consultancy		

Int. 2	<p>A tool that would find metaphors or historical trends in large corpora of literature.</p> <p>A tool that would help to visualise and explore literary corpora. (explorative research)</p>	To help clients to be more open-minded in their business by exploring prevalent trends addressed in literature.
Reference to Source	“I would love to work across [texts]. If a client brought me a corpus and said, what can we do? What kind of distant reading can we do with this corpus? I would be all over [it]. In some ways, that would be a dream assignment.”	
Int. 4	<p>A system that would recommend books to read to cope with stress, grief, etc.</p> <p>A tool that would help finding important archetypes.</p> <p>A tool that would help researching past or present texts on developments in technology.</p> <p>A tool that would organise and create an overview of a large literary corpus (better “signposting”).</p>	<p>To use literature as a self-help coach or mentor to deal with e.g. stress or grief.</p> <p>To improve collaboration among teams by understanding what archetypes they fall into and how to avoid them.</p> <p>To understand reactions and behaviours around new technological developments in the past and in the present (e.g. electrification). And build role-play scenarios to act out and understand the future of technology (e.g. AI).</p> <p>To find useful fictional resources in large corpora that are otherwise difficult to navigate to engage the clients/audience e.g. during presentations.</p>
Reference to Source	“then I think there’s a signposting issue because there’s so much literature in the world to even know when and where to look. It’s not just an easy search for a title or keyword search, noun association. If I wanted to know more about this, and I was open to literary sources as well as other ones, where would I start that kind of signposting to something?”	
Journalism		
Int. 6	A tool that is easily accessible and works fast to process large amounts of digitised texts.	To do research for articles and features (mostly to search through historical narratives).
Reference to Source	“Yeah, anything that can be accessed from a laptop, I think, can enrich someone’s work and would gain traction [...] As long as it’s quick and easily accessible and useful, I think, that’s always going to be of value.”	
Int. 8	A tool that would help to get through a lot more material (historical or literary) more quickly.	To build a podcast and write articles backed by more literature to better engage the audience.
Reference to Source	“So if I had used more of digital humanities, using the tools properly, I could have gotten through a lot more. So there’s a speed element”	

Int. 12	A tool that could visualise the data in a large corpus of fiction.	For research, to know where the gaps are, what topics to write about. Solving the problem of needing to learn literature.
Reference to Source	“It could be that the body of literature is the greatest data visualisation which would be available[...] I think the prospect is absolutely wonderful. But the prospect is, as I hear you describing it there, that we would all be Borges, but we wouldn’t have to spend [time] learning 10-20 languages and spend every waking hour in the library.”	
Int. 13	A tool that could identify important cultural themes, tensions, behaviours, and metaphors used.	To describe technology, understanding people’s behaviour around it, and understand the language (Metaverse, flashing computer lights, “the street finds its own uses for things”...)
Reference to Source	“it might only be imagining something five or ten years out, which I think is quite interesting as a fictional move, rather than thinking that it has to be 500 or 3000 years in the future that you can actually get something that allows you to explore really challenging subjects and in a quite transformed world.”	
Medical Humanities and Therapy		
Int. 5	A tool that would identify metaphors, stylistic features, sentiments	To characterise experiences of illness as described in literary and/or autobiographical texts or in online fora or to explore the ethical implications of advancements in medicine (e.g. pregnancy outside of the body) through novels (e.g. <i>Frankenstein</i> , <i>Brave New World</i> , etc.)
Reference to Source	“I became interested in a phenomenon that in stylistics is known as ‘mind style’, which basically is the way in which linguistic patterns give the reader a sense of a mind, a character’s mind, that works in a way that is foregrounded and that is central to how you understand that work of fiction and what it might be doing.”	
Int. 10	A tool that could uncover archetypes, imagery, repetitions, metaphors	Find relevant folktales and stories to work with patients to achieve therapeutic outcome
Reference to Source	“Yeah, I would love there to be a source of stories. Because I do a lot of searching to find stories, a lot of buying of books.”	
Policymaking		
Int. 1	A tool that would help to understand the literature of the Irish islands. A tool that would help to find literature relevant to a strategy or topic.	Irish policymakers, who are often unaware of life on the islands, can develop political strategies with a better understanding for them. Back up and explain policy decisions with literary narratives as evidence.
Reference	“And you see that, don’t you, in the big set pieces, aside from quoting Seamus	

to Source	Heaney all the time, there is an understanding in an Irish context of the importance of literature and a value placed on that in terms of building relationships, in terms of couching messages, often very subtle messages, and supporting overall communication.”	
Int. 3	A tool that identifies topics, concerns, tensions in fiction.	To make informed decisions understanding the emotions of conflicting sides, with a particular focus on Northern Ireland and the troubles.
Reference to Source	“The poetry in Northern Ireland is particularly strong as a way of people voicing their experiences. And to the point where, probably Seamus Heaney in particular, is kind of pillaged for speeches and so on”	
Int. 9	<p>A tool that could go through personal narratives and uncover prevalent topics or concerns.</p> <p>A tool that would help with research on understudied texts (e.g. written by women), and understand the emotions of that story.</p>	<p>To work on the “Life Events” project by the Department of Public Expenditure and Reform, Citizens Information (https://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/my-situation/lifeevents/)</p> <p>To use descriptions of suffering as evidence for policy making (e.g. suffering in mother and baby homes, women in the military, etc.)</p>
Reference to Source	“If you look at something like that tragic inquiry that’s going to have to start in the Defence Forces at the minute, or you look at mother and baby homes, [...] where increasingly part of the data set is the stories. [...] they’ll record the hurt or whatever they felt. And that, initially, is evidence. But long term it’s actually using data for policy creation because the stories that were published at the weekend about abuse of women in the army, that will probably be more powerful in creating policy change than stats could ever be.”	
Publishing		
Int. 7	A tool that would help identifying author’s tics	To improve and speed up the editing process. (They already use <i>Phrasefinder</i> , but a CLS stylistic-focussed tool might improve that)
Reference to Source	“I don’t know if that’s the name for it, but it’s like a word search. But instead of using just one word, you can put in groups of two words [...] or however many words you want. So you can see if a writer has a tic”	
Int. 11	Wouldn’t use fiction or CLS tools	-
Reference to Source	“We do, on occasion, try to get trends in as much as we can, but in many ways, every book is an individual[...] You’re starting at ground zero every time in a lot of genres, but not in all.”	

Figure 2. User Stories Table.

4.2 Technical implications

Based on the user needs and requirements in the table above the following tools and approaches seem like they would be most likely to benefit the non-academic use of computational literary studies.

- **Corpus building:** Many of the interviewees implied the need for custom digital corpora, which may or may not be difficult to build due to the nature of these works as not digitally available, available only in fragmentary, non-standardised sources, and/or under copyright restrictions to use. These constraints could be addressed in the future through a wider implementation of the CLS INFRA Programmable Corpora approach, and/or the realisation of the use of Derived Text Formats explored in the project's Deliverable 7.4. In addition, participants mentioned the need for.
- **Customisation and extension of NLP tools:** Many of the needs expressed by the potential users imply a desire for functionalities that are still very difficult or indeed impossible for computational literary studies to realise. This is in some cases due to the vagueness of their specifications, and in some cases due to the linguistic complexity of the processing they imagine (exploring metaphors, for example). The convergence of these needs with technological possibilities could be enhanced through the wider dissemination of the CLS INFRA WP4 Training materials and the further development of the WP8 toolkit. In detail, participants mentioned:
 - **Visualisations:** Some participants, e.g. from journalism (int 12), are interested in exploratory research through visualisations of literary data. The participants would need to specify what they would be looking for in the corpus or what angle they would explore it from.
 - **Stylistic features:** Some participants (int 7, int 5) are particularly interested in exploring the style of literature.
 - **Images, concepts and metaphors.** As mentioned above.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Overall, the CLS INFRA interviewees' attitudes were overwhelmingly positive towards the potential for their fields to implement the use of literature and CLS tools in their work. Roughly 67% could definitely see themselves using CLS tools adapted to their professional needs, and the remaining participants (with one exception) were not opposed to it but would need better adaptation of the tools to their needs. The interviews showed us that in spite of our preparation to speak in practical terms about how literature might be used across a range of application areas, the practical implications of taking it on themselves still seemed rather far removed from reality for our interviewees. The demand for it is not necessarily there, not yet at least, with fiction more viewed as an addition and a potential enrichment in these professional fields⁴ rather than a core tool. If we can generalise, the biggest issue being expressed was that many professions have their established systems dictating how their work needs to be done, and while they like to imagine implementing more literature and fiction, in the end, unless a CLS research infrastructure could show that there would be an immediately visible benefit to using their tools, implementation of these methods would not be attractive enough to bring in these new users. In the following list we summarise some of the main general recommendations, focussing not just on functionalities but on the context of use, that emerged from the CLS INFRA interviews:

Case Studies and Pilot Examples: The project material, such as tools, should be more accessible for professionals from outside of academia, and the applications for each field should be visible. Ideally, we would present applications through case studies and pilot examples relevant to each professional requirement to have the respective group start implementing CLS tools, as suggested by a policymaker: "It'll be good if you could in the doing of this maybe take something as a case study, and maybe try and illustrate how this resource could be layered in" (int 1). Similarly, a participant working in consultancy also expressed enthusiasm towards implementing more distant reading tools and literature in theory, but would require more conversations to develop practical workflows: "I would love to do that. And we should set up, when you have the bandwidth for a further conversation to discuss in more practical terms what that might look like. That would be gratifying for me" (int 2).

Methods and tools need to be practical, fast, and accessible: Besides needing case studies, pilot examples, and further conversations for how to use CLS for the participants' professions, the participants would also need to see the practicality and efficiency of CLS methods. A participant from policymaking noted that "[t]he policymaker's work is all about solving problems in a very practical way" (int 1), thus applying needs to be practical to problem-solving in the policy sphere. A journalist who often had to contend with fast-paced work environments added the CLS workflow in their profession would need to be "quick and easily accessible and useful," in which case applying literature will "be of value" (int 6). Accessibility is also compromised by users often not knowing how to navigate the sheer quantity of literature: "And then I think there's a signposting problem because there's so much literature in the world to even know when where to look. It's not just an easy search for a title

⁴ except for participants from the field of publishing who struggled to see obvious benefits of these applications of fiction in their work, and saw more benefits in personal application of literature, such as literature as capacity building, i.e. "reading fiction makes for a better human being" (int 11)

or keyword search, noun association. If I wanted to know more about this, and I was open to literary sources as well as other ones, where would I start that kind of signposting to something?” (int 4)

Advantages need to be crystallised and sold: Once the practicality and benefit of the tools for each profession is highlighted, it needs to be sold to the target audience, or as a participant from policy making suggests:

So at one end of that, then, you need to create a demand. Because I think, speaking frankly, unless you know more than I do, that demand probably isn't really there at the moment[...] But in approaching them, you'd have to pay attention and think through how this could help policy. You'd have to, what I call, crystallise the offer. You'd have to think about, well, in what way could the source that you're building—obviously, very significant, looking at the investment and the range of institutions that are involved in it—it needs somebody to give some specific thought to how it could support, or inform, or evaluate—but I prefer support—the policy landscape. I probably don't need to say this, but very often the discourse coming out of academia—and there's nothing wrong with this—but it's of a critical nature, and that's where the humanities position themselves. But as a policymaker, that's just not much use to me. It's of limited use. I'd much prefer someone to say, okay, well, I don't like that and to understand a bit about the constraints. There are endlessly critical voices, you know, it interrupts relationships. (int 1)

Thus, to bridge the gap between academia and beyond academia, the frame and language of what CLS methods offer to professionals beyond academia has to be phrased in a more accessible way. A participant from journalism, who also with her work bridges the gap between academia and an audience beyond academia, noted that the offer of CLS methods in and beyond academia would also have to be pitched to people at the university to facilitate collaboration:

From my experience at the university or from my experience of dragging people with you into something forward-looking, I think they'll be cautious. I still think it should be said. So it would be more about selling it. More showing and having those examples. I think something like the Cassandra Project, and he speaks so passionately about it, is just a really good way of seeing. It's not as powerful on paper. And then you hear someone talk it through. So examples that worked. And then the actual skills to use the resources. So training in terms in that technical sense particularly. (int 8)

Build relationships with professionals from target sectors: A policymaker (int 1) and a medical humanist (int 5) each emphasised the importance of building relationships into the target professional fields (“the crucial thing is to collaborate with people who work in the field where, ideally, we would like to make the difference” (int 5)), and to start having conversations with them as early as possible (“now is the time to start building those relationships[...]you build those relationships for the long term[...] ‘identify the relevant players’” (int 1)). However, they also warned that relationship building can take a long time: “it's not easy to get started. It took me a long time to get started with that because it takes time to build trust with the people in health care, they are very busy, and it takes a while to build your networks[...]” (int 5).

Nevertheless, “now is the time to start building those relationships[...]you build those relationships for the long term[...] ‘identify the relevant players.’” (int 1). Knowing the timing of when to start building those relationships can be challenging because “[g]o too early with it, they’ll say, well, what’s all that? If you come too late, it’s too late” (int 1). However, regardless of when we approach these professionals, we would need “to pitch it as a potential resource” (int 1) and “pay specific attention to how to connect with policy, and that’s got to be people who are in the system at the moment” (int 1). Then “there is huge potential, but you do need to do it in collaboration and also be patient and persistent at the same time, because sometimes it takes a while to get to the right people or to hit the right moment when somebody is ready to hear what you’ve got to say” (int 5).

CLS methods but with historical texts: Some participants liked what CLS tools had to offer, but would prefer using more historical texts e.g. from historical archives (int 6 and int 9). A policymaker mentioned that historical texts also contain stories which are important for policy making, and they would see merit using CLS methods to explore and extract information from those stories:

If you look at the role of the National Archives in 15, 20 years and say, ‘how can it add value from digital?’ I think what you’re talking about is what they should be thinking about and their strategizing. [...] And I know it’s not a literary archive in the way your project is, like going to 18th-century Romantic poets, or whatever it happens to be. But those stories, those stories of women who were abused in the army, that’s part of our future history. If you’re teaching children in school about how to value each other, goodness me, taking quotes from that; you couldn’t get anything more powerful than that (int 9)

Historical text analysis is currently not within the focus of the CLS INFRA project, but could be considered for the future development of CLS tools.

To realise and systematise more applications of fiction and CLS tools in and beyond academia, we would need to take into account the points mentioned in this section for the future development of a CLS infrastructure. For the long term future, we would also need to take into account that the user needs may change and evolve over the time until the tools are developed and properly implemented in the system of these professionals, so it requires ongoing communication. While it was challenging to speak to participants about how precise applications of CLS tools might be adopted in their work, we need to start these conversations now to inspire imaginaries around potential uses and to know the market to which our project has to adapt in order to expand its user base in a sustainable and meaningful way.

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Annex: Interview Questions

Part 1: Sectoral experience using literature and analytics

1a. Do fictional narratives have a function in your work or your field, and if so, what is it?

If yes, can you give an example? If no, can you say why you think this is not the case?

1b. Do you distinguish different “types” of fiction, i.e. are some works of fiction more useful or informative than others? Which ones are important for your work?

1c. What do you think the strengths and/or weaknesses of using literature in this way would be?

2a. Do data mining or data analytics tools have a function in your work or your field, and if so, what is it? Can you give an example?

2b. If so, what data sources do you use and how do you test them for quality/relevance?

2c. What do you think the strengths and/or weaknesses of data analytics are?

Part 2: Our four models of applied literary studies

“As a part of the work on this project, we have been looking at applications of literature and/or fictional narratives to address real world applications. We would like to present you briefly with some of the types we have found, and get your responses to them. We have found a number of basic models by which fictional narratives can be used: “

1. We call the first of these ‘Literature as evidence of the past and present.’

For example, in order to understand the social milieu of the city of Tangier, a researcher used the various perspectives of authors writing about it, saying that one could gather different points of view and experiences of Tangier, depending on whether travellers, immigrants, or natives were writing about it.

1a. Do you think this is an appropriate use of fiction narratives?

1b. Could you imagine or do you know a similar type of application in your own work or

field?

2. We call the second of these ‘Literature as a predictive model.’

An example of this is the “Cassandra project” of the German military, which uses literary production to uncover clashes of culture, and through them predict and potentially prevent the outbreak of real life hostilities in sensitive regions.

2a. Do you think this is an appropriate use of fiction narratives?

2b. Could you imagine or do you know a similar type of application in your own work or field?

3. We call the third of these ‘Literature as prototyping the future.’

An example of this are science fiction novels that described future technologies and inspired inventions, such as the U.S. Navy’s first submarines, the modern helicopter, mobile communicators, mitochondrial reproduction techniques...

3a. Do you think this is an appropriate use of fiction narratives?

3b. Could you imagine or do you know a similar type of application in your own work or field?

4. We call the fourth of these ‘Literature as capacity building.’

Examples of this exist in the practices of narrative medicine, which uses fictional stories to contribute to the training of doctors, helping them to be more imaginative and empathetic.

OR

Many studies have shown that literature is a very good way of teaching empathy. A further 2016 study has shown that empathy can be a key factor in successful political negotiations.

4a. Do you think this is an appropriate use of fiction narratives?

4b. Could you imagine or do you know a similar type of application in your own work or field?

5. In some of these examples the approach is to use these fictional narratives in a large corpus, rather than just as single works, and to analyse them using software tools. Does this make a difference in how you perceive the impact of the fictionality of the input texts? Why or why not?

Part 3: CLS and Literature as sectorial evidence

“Using large scale collections of literature as data to be analysed is an approach we call computational literary studies, or CLS. CLS research generally requires clean and legally available input data, and software tools able to analyse it.”

1. Were your organisation to adopt the use of literature in one or more of the ways we describe above, would there be any competencies or resources you or your organisation would need so as to be able to use this kind of approach?